

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT IN PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

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Аннотация

Мазкур мақолада психологик ривожланишда ижтимоий муҳитнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти таҳлил қилинади. Ижтимоий муҳит инсоннинг шахсий хусусиятлари, психик жараёнлари ва ижтимоий фаоллиги шаклланишида муҳим роль ўйнайди. Мақолада ижтимоий муҳитнинг турли компонентлари — оила, мактаб, дўстлар муҳити, жамоатчилик ва маданий муҳитнинг психологик ривожланишга таъсири кўриб чиқилади. Шунингдек, ижтимоий муҳитдаги ижобий ва салбий таъсирлар, уларнинг шахс ривожланишига таъсири бартараф этиш чоралари муҳокама қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: психологик ривожланиш, ижтимоий муҳит, оила, мактаб, ижтимоий тажриба, шахсий ўсиш, ижтимоий қўллаб-қувватлаш.

Аннотация

В данной статье анализируется роль и значение социальной среды в психологическом развитии личности. Социальная среда играет важную роль в формировании личностных качеств, психических процессов и социальной активности человека. В статье рассматривается влияние различных компонентов социальной среды — семьи, школы, окружения друзей, общества и культурной среды — на психологическое развитие. Также обсуждаются как положительные, так и отрицательные влияния социальной среды, а также меры по нейтрализации их воздействия на развитие личности.

Ключевые слова: психологическое развитие, социальная среда, семья, школа, социальный опыт, личностный рост, социальная поддержка.

Abstract

This article analyzes the role and importance of the social environment in psychological development. The social environment plays a significant role in shaping an individual's personal traits, mental processes, and social activity. The article explores the impact of various components of the social environment — family, school, peer environment, society, and cultural context — on psychological development. It also discusses both positive and negative influences of the social environment and the strategies to mitigate their impact on individual development.

Keywords: psychological development, social environment, family, school, social experience, personal growth, social support.

Psychological development is the process of gradual formation and improvement of a person's personal characteristics, abilities, as well as emotional and social abilities. That is, at each stage of a person's life, his mental state, feelings and social activity develop differently. The role of the social environment in this process is invaluable, since contacts and relationships with others affect a person's mental health, thinking ability and the process of adaptation to society.

The social environment serves to develop a person's cognitive activity, that is, mental processes such as understanding, memory, attention and decision-making. It also ensures a person's mental stability, that is, increases the ability to withstand stress and difficulties. Through this

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environment, a person finds his place in society, learns social norms and adapts to them. This process is called social adaptation.

Psychological development continues throughout a person's life - from childhood to adulthood. It has its own characteristics at different ages, for example, in childhood there are more emotional and emotional changes, while in adolescence the person's self-awareness and social skills develop[1]. Therefore, psychological development is a complex and dynamic process consisting of several stages.

The main areas of psychological development include cognitive (mental) development, emotional development, motivation (desires and pursuit of goals), and social development. These areas are closely interconnected and ensure the success and stability of a person in his personal and social life.

The social environment is one of the most important factors influencing the development of a person's mental functions and internal abilities. Relationships with people in the environment, positive or negative experiences gained from them, affect the future mental and social state of a person.

The social environment is the environment that includes social relations, rules, norms and institutions surrounding a person. It includes the following:

- The family is the first social environment, providing the child's initial spiritual and social development.
 - Schools and educational institutions - along with learning, teach social rules, relationships and a culture of communication.
 - The environment of friends and colleagues - an important source of social experience and personal identification.
 - The public and cultural environment - a system of general culture, rules, values and beliefs.
- The social environment affects the psychological development of a person in various ways:
- Social learning: a person observes those around him, learns from them and adjusts himself (A. Bandura's social learning theory).
 - Reflection and self-awareness: the social environment provides an opportunity for a person to evaluate and develop himself.
 - Emotional support: the social environment helps a person to maintain emotional stability.
 - Motivation and aspirations: the social environment inspires a person to pursue various goals.

The family is the first social environment of a child and is of great importance in his spiritual and social development. The child's first experiences in life, personal and emotional characteristics are formed mainly in the family environment. In this process, the behavior of parents, their love for the child, support and methods of upbringing play a large role. All these factors directly affect the child's level of self-esteem, emotional stability and the formation of social skills.

Scientific research in the field of psychology shows that children who grow up in a positive, loving and stable family environment have a high level of stress tolerance, that is, the ability to cope with psychological problems. In addition, such children also develop social skills - the ability to establish effective relationships with others, solve problems and adapt to society. These skills are an important factor in the child's future success in life and overcoming problems.

The love and upbringing methods in the family also affect the psychological health and inner world of the child. For example, a child who feels the interest of his parents and is encouraged is able

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to behave stably even in difficult situations, maintaining a positive emotional state. This contributes to his success in social relationships[2].

School is not only a place to acquire knowledge and skills, but also an environment for the child to learn and develop social relationships. Here, students are in constant contact with teachers, colleagues and team members, express themselves socially, and test their abilities. The school environment allows children to express their feelings, solve problems and find their place in the team.

A positive and supportive school environment increases student interest in the learning process. In this case, students are involved not only in knowledge in the lessons, but also in social activity. For example, participation in team work, sports competitions and cultural events develops their sense of responsibility and teaches them to cooperate in a team[3]. Such activity leads to the student's personal growth and social success.

At the same time, a positive school environment enhances a child's self-awareness and improves their self-esteem. Students feel supported and valued, increasing their emotional stability and motivation. These factors create the basis for the student's overall development and future success in social life.

Friends and social groups are of particular importance in the lives of young people. They not only serve as an environment for interests and spending time, but also play an important role in the development of a person's self-awareness and the formation of social skills. Relationships with friends allow young people to share their thoughts and feelings, which strengthens their emotional health.

Social groups provide young people with the opportunity to try out their social role and find their place in the community. For example, activities with group members develop young people's ability to cooperate, solve problems, and balance relationships in a team. In this process, young people learn social rules and learn to adapt to them, which increases their social activity and stability.

Friends and social groups strengthen young people's ability to express themselves and control their emotions. Young people affirm their identity by expressing the thoughts and views that are important to them, which strengthens their self-understanding and emotional stability. Positive experiences in the social environment have a positive effect on young people's mental health and prepare them to adapt to society.

The cultural and social environment plays an important role in the psychological development of a person. Culture shapes a person's value system, plays a key role in their sense of place in society, and their sense of self. Each person identifies himself through his cultural environment, that is, he has an understanding of who he is and to which society he belongs. This process is important in harmonizing a person's inner world and external relationships.

The social environment also affects a person's psychological state and his attitude to life. For example, customs, traditions, and social norms in society give direction to a person's views and behavior. By acting in accordance with these norms, a person feels like a member of society, which ensures psychological stability.

Through cultural and social influences, a person finds meaning in his life, which plays an important role in his personal growth and striving for self-development. Culture not only provides a person with unique values and ideas, but also creates the necessary conditions for mental health and social adaptation through relationships in the social environment.

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Cultural and social influences have a strong impact on the psychological development and adaptation of young people to society, shaping their attitude to life and strengthening their mental stability.

Negative factors in the social environment can have a serious impact on the psychological development of young people. Among these, situations such as violence, psychological pressure, social isolation, aggression, etc. occupy a special place. For example, violence and aggression can lead to psychological problems such as stress, fear, anxiety and depression in young people. Psychological pressure and social isolation also cause a person to self-harm, have low self-esteem and withdraw from social contacts.

Effective measures should be taken at the family, school and community levels to reduce and combat such negative influences. It is important to create an environment of love and support for young people in the family, pay attention to their feelings, and anticipate and reduce psychological risks. If psychological support and counseling centers are established in schools, students will have the opportunity to openly discuss their problems. At the same time, teachers and educators should conduct educational work against violence among young people.

At the community level, youth support systems should be developed through psychological services, trainings, and protective measures. It is also necessary to disseminate information about negative influences through social networks and the media, and to raise awareness among young people about mental health and social responsibility.

Eliminating negative factors in the social environment is of great importance in ensuring the psychological stability and social development of young people. Therefore, each social institution - family, school, and community - should work together and effectively organize psychological assistance and support.

The social environment plays a decisive role in the psychological development of a person. Family, school, friends, and community are the main factors in this process. Positive influences in the social environment strengthen the psychological stability of a person and help to reveal his potential. At the same time, protecting against negative factors and creating a positive environment is an important task of society.

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